

Research Article

RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for the Estimation of Dolutegravir In Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

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This work proposed to develop and validate a reverse phase high-performance liquid chromatography method to measure dolutegravir in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. In statistically organised trials, a number of method components, such as mobile phase ratio and column type, were changed to assess how these factors affected the chromatographic separation of dolutegravir. The separation was carried out at room temperature under isocratic conditions using Methanol: 0.05% OPA (pH 3.0) (68:32) at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min on a Kromasil C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm). A PDA detector was used to measure the maximum absorbance as 258 nm. While the run time was only five minutes, the retention time was 2.650 minutes. The calibration curve was linear in the concentration range of 2.5–15 µg/mL. The calculated LOQ of 0.24 µg/mL and the measured LOD of 0.08 µg/mL show how sensitive the new method is. The robustness and ruggedness of the method were validated by the %RSD being less than 2. The test percentage for formulation analysis was 99.30. This method was therefore widely used to evaluate Dolutegravir in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations.

Keywords: Dolutegravir, Limit of Detection, Limit of Quantitation, Bulk and Formulation.

INTRODUCTION

Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection is treated with Dolutegravir. Dolutegravir belongs to a group of drugs known as HIV integrase inhibitors. It functions by raising the quantity of immune cells that aid in the body's defence against infections and lowering the level of HIV in blood. ^[1] Dolutegravir is a second-generation HIV Integrase Strand Transfer Inhibitor (INSTI). It stops the HIV virus from multiplying by binding to the active site of the viral enzyme integrase and blocking it, which prevents the virus from inserting its genetic material into the DNA of the host's CD4 immune cells. ^[2] Only a few analytical (limited to 50 mg only) and bioanalytical methods have been developed thus far for the

determination of dolutegravir in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation. Dolutegravir's chemical structure ^[3] is shown in Figure 01.

Figure 01: The Chemical structure of Dolutegravir

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents

The working standard drug Dolutegravir (99% purity) was obtained from Hetero Labs Limited, Hyderabad, Telangana. The formulation dosage form having brand name Tivicay PD 5 mg containing 5 mg of Dolutegravir, was purchased from local Pharmacy. HPLC grade Methanol, Water and Acetonitrile & Orthophosphoric acid (OPA) were purchased from Merk chemicals private limited, Mumbai.

Preparation of Mobile Phase

Methanol:0.05% OPA (68:32) at pH 3.0 was prepared. Before being utilised, the mobile phase was filtered through a 0.22 µm nylon filter after being sonicated for 15 minutes to eliminate dissolved gases.

Preparation of standard drug solution

Dolutegravir, 5 mg was weighed and transfer into a 10mL volumetric flask. It was then dissolved in 5 mL of methanol using a sonicator to make sure it was fully dissolved. The mixture was filtered using a 0.22 µm nylon filter. After that the volume in the flask was adjusted to 10 mL using methanol. This resulted in a stock solution that has 500 µg/mL of Dolutegravir. The stock solution of Dolutegravir was diluted to 50 µg/mL and then to 5µg/mL. The 5µg/mL of Dolutegravir were required for developing and validating a method.

Preparation of formulation solution

After carefully weighing ten Dolutegravir tablets (5 mg according to the label), they were ground into a fine powder. A 10 mL volumetric flask was filled with 5 mg of Dolutegravir tablet powder, the flask was filled with about 5 mL of methanol, and the mixture was sonicated for 15 minutes. After the solution had cooled to room temperature, the volume was adjusted using the same diluent. A sample stock solution of 500 µg/mL was prepared. A 0.22 µm nylon filter was used to filter the sample stock solution, and the first few ml of the filtrate were discarded. A working sample solution of 50 µg/mL was prepared by carefully pipetting 1.0 mL of the filtered sample stock solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluting it to volume with the diluent. To reach the necessary concentration of 5 µg/mL for assay and validation testing, further dilutions were produced from the working sample solution using the same diluent.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT

Selection of Wavelength

The PDA detector was used to scan reference solutions containing 5µg/mL in order to choose an appropriate wavelength. The maximal wavelength obtained was found to be the optimal wavelength for the detection.

Table 01: Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Parameter	Condition
Mobile Phase	Methanol: 0.05% OPA (pH 3.0) (68:32)
Column	Kromasil C18 (150 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm)
Flow Rate	0.8 ml/min
Wavelength	258nm
Injection Volume	10 µL
Temperature	Ambient
Run time	5 min

Method Validation

In accordance with the ICH standards, the method's specificity, system appropriateness, LOD & LOQ, linearity, accuracy, precision, ruggedness, and robustness were all validated. Duplicate injections of

the sample and standard solutions into the column were used for validation.^[4,5]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method Development

Figure 02: UV Spectra of Dolutegravir

Figure 03: Optimized Chromatogram of Dolutegravir

Table 02: Results for Optimized Chromatogram

S.NO	Drug	Retention Time (min)	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
1	Dolutegravir	2.650	6850	1.11

Method Validation

No inference of diluent & Placebo

Specificity

Figure 04: Chromatogram of Blank

Figure 05: Chromatogram of Placebo

Linearity

Table 03: Results for Linearity

S. No	Level	Dolutegravir	
		Concentration in $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Peak Area
1	Level 1	2.5	54210
2	Level 2	5	108432
3	Level 3	7.5	162543
4	Level 4	10	216854
5	Level 5	12.5	271102
6	Level 6	15	325450

Figure 06: Linearity graph for Dolutegravir

LOD & LOQ

Dolutegravir 's LOD was found to be $0.08\mu\text{g/mL}$, while its LOQ was determined to be $0.24\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Precision

The system and method precision % RSD for dolutegravir were found to be 0.31 and 0.15, respectively. Both the system and method precision %RSDs fell within the permissible range of less than 2. As a result, the developed process was thought to be precise.

Table 04: Results for Precision

S.NO	Injection	System Precision		Method Precision	
		Retention Time	Peak Area	Retention Time	Peak Area
1	Injection-1	2.647	107976	2.652	107684
2	Injection-2	2.650	108292	2.648	107359
3	Injection-3	2.656	107886	2.653	107760
4	Injection-4	2.649	107486	2.654	107832
5	Injection-5	2.655	107267	2.649	107476
6	Injection-6	2.652	107959	2.651	107593
Mean		2.6515	107811	2.651167	107617.3
STD		0.003202	338.5449	0.002115	162.3696
%RSD		0.12	0.31	0.08	0.15

Accuracy

The recovery percentage was found to be between 98.40 and 99.60%. At 50%, 100%, and 150% spiking levels, the percentage RSD was determined to be

within the permissible limit for dolutegravir. The results showed that the suggested method was accurate, with an acceptance limit of 98–102% and a percentage RSD of less than two.

Table 05: Results for Accuracy

Recovery Level	Concentration in µg/ml			Amount Found	% Recovery	% RSD
	Target	Spiked	Total			
50%	2.5	1.25	3.75	3.69	98.40	0.33
	2.5	1.25	3.75	3.71	98.93	
	2.5	1.25	3.75	3.72	99.20	
100%	2.5	2.5	5.0	4.96	99.20	0.41
	2.5	2.5	5.0	4.93	98.60	
	2.5	2.5	5.0	4.98	99.60	
150%	2.5	3.75	6.25	6.21	99.36	0.20
	2.5	3.75	6.25	6.18	98.88	
	2.5	3.75	6.25	6.20	99.20	

Ruggedness (Intermediate Precision)

%RSD of less than two is required to characterize ruggedness. In the developed approach, dolutegravir's

%RSD was 0.23. The ruggedness of the method is confirmed by results that are within the allowed range.

Table 06: Results for Ruggedness

S. No	Injection	Retention Time	Peak Area
1	Injection-1	2.652	107939
2	Injection-2	2.649	107782
3	Injection-3	2.650	107867
4	Injection-4	2.656	108375
5	Injection-5	2.645	107597
6	Injection-6	2.655	108125
Mean		2.651167	107947.5
STD		0.003716	248.6817
%RSD		0.14	0.23

Robustness

It was confirmed that the Dolutegravir percentage change using the developed approach was within the allowed range of less than 2. Thus, it was

demonstrated that when the analytical conditions were significantly altered, the suggested approach was appropriate for the analysis of dolutegravir. This shows that the results are unaffected by even small changes to the analytical conditions.

Table 07: Results for Robustness

S. No	Condition	Dolutegravir		
		Retention Time	Peak Area	% Change
1	Standard	2.650	108432	--
2	+MP (73:27)	2.649	108312	0.11
3	-MP (63:37)	2.651	108539	0.09
4	+Flow Rate 0.82ml/min	2.648	108196	0.21
5	-Flow rate 0.78ml/min	2.652	108575	0.13
%RSD		0.06	0.15	

Assay

Dolutegravir's test percentage in formulation analysis was 99.30%. As a result, it was demonstrated that the

technique was appropriate for routine analysis of Dolutegravir in both bulk and formulation form.

Table 08: Results for Formulation

S. No	Drug	Brand	Label Claim	Peak Area	Amount Found	% Assay
1	Dolutegravir	Tivicay PD	5 mg	107682	4.965mg	99.30

Figure 07: Chromatogram of Formulation

CONCLUSION

The HPLC measurement of dolutegravir in pharmaceutical formulations was not well documented in the literature priorly. A sensitive, accurate, and precise RP-HPLC method for assessing dolutegravir in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations has been developed. The recommended RP-HPLC method for the Dolutegravir was shown to be suitable

for routine quantitative analysis following validation. The low standard deviation data show the exceptionally high precision of the new approach. The linearity, accuracy, specificity, and precision values were judged to be within reasonable boundaries. The chromatogram's lack of extra peaks showed that there was no conflict between the tablet's common excipients. Thus, it is shown that the revised RP-HPLC method is straightforward, linear, precise,

sensitive, and reproducible. The new approach is therefore simple to use and offers a fast analytical time for routine quality monitoring of Dolutegravir in bulk and pharmaceutical formulations. The given findings demonstrate the high precision and accuracy of the suggested approach.

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